

AN ELLIPTICAL CONSTRUCTION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK PROVERBS

Gofurova Mavluda Botirjon kizi

KSPI lecturer

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7798457>

Annotation: The article reveals through examples and rates that an Elliptical construction is a sentence in which one or more words are dropped for brevity, this inaction is also called elision, the meaning of an abbreviated sentence should still be clear based on the surrounding context. Article learn and compare proverbs in English and uzbek languages, types of Elliptical construction.

Key words: elliptical construction, sentence, shortened sentence, 'omission'

Ellipsis (Greek — omission, lack) — omission of an element from the structure of a syntactic device in a speech or text, structural "lack", "incompleteness" of a syntactic device. Ellipsis arises on the basis of the requirement of economy (thriftiness) and does not interfere with the main task of the language - conveying the necessary information. This situation is related to the speech situation, where the omitted language unit is understood from the rest of the syntactic device (for example, the use of expressions "Salim - 3, Nadir - 5" in evaluating students is an ellipsis). Ellipsis is usually used as a stylistic figure. In fiction, ellipsis is often found in dialogic speech, and is also widely used in folk proverbs, wise sayings, and phraseology. For example from Uzbek language, it is not difficult to find out which words have been omitted, i.e., ellipsised, from the full text of the proverb " Birniki — mingga, mingniki — tumanga /One is to a thousand, and a thousand is to region" " The kindness of one person touches a thousand people, the kindness of a thousand people touches a hundred thousand people. Phrases such as "He who heard overcame" are also the result of Ellipsis (the word "man" is omitted).

An elliptical construction is a sentence from which one or more words are omitted for the sake of conciseness. This act of omission is also called elision. The meaning of the shortened sentence should still be clear, however, based on the surrounding context. For instance from English language: "I went to the movies, but Jerry did not." We know that the thing Jerry did not do was "go to the movies," but we omit it as part of this elliptical construction. The meaning of the sentence does not change with the elliptical clause omitted.

A noun ellipsis removes a noun from a sentence. For instance: "I did a full homework, and May did too". This sentence removes the phrase "a full homework" from its second independent clause. So the sentence is not diminishing the understanding.

A verb ellipsis omits a verb from a sentence. For instance: I drank water and Frale Milk. The verb "drank" appears only once but it refers to both "I" and "Frale".

A verb phrase ellipsis omits an entire phrase that's anchored by a verb. For instance: "I went to the park, but Jim did not". We know that the thing Jim did do was "do to the park", but we omit it as part of this elliptical construction. The meaning of the sentence remained same.

There are numerous widely acknowledged types of ellipsis. They include, as mentioned and briefly illustrated below:

1. Gapping: John can play the guitar, and Mary can play the violin.
2. Stripping: John can play the guitar, and Mary can play the guitar, too.
3. Verb phrase ellipsis: The man who wanted to order the salmon did order the salmon.
4. Pseudogapping: They could read this book more easily than they could read that book.
5. Answer ellipsis: When does the circus start? A: The circus starts Tomorrow.
6. Sluicing: Something unusual happened. B: What happened?
7. Nominal ellipsis: I heard Mary's dog, and you heard Bill's dog.
8. Comparative deletion: William has friends in more countries than you have friends in countries.
9. Null complement anaphora: They told Bill to help, but he refused to help.

Among experts, there is no unanimity that all of the abovementioned syntaxes form a natural class in the sense of being derived by one and the same mechanism. Ellipsis-based accounts have been given for other syntaxes, and some of the above have been analyzed in other ways. Most experts would agree, however, that most of the above items are in fact ellipses, so the discussion below takes their status as ellipses largely for granted.

The example sentences below employ the convention whereby the elided material is indicated with subscripts and smaller font size. All examples given below come from English though similar patterns arise cross-linguistically, with variation from language to language.

Elliptical construction in Uzbek language(based on the word “Ko'p”)

1. Yo'qotganingni ko'pdan so'ra/ Ko'p ko'makka yaxshi, Oz — barakka
2. Ko'kka boqma, ko'pga boq/ Ko'pdan ayrilgan ozar, Ko'pga qo'shilgan o'zar
3. Ko'p duosi ko'l bo'lur/ Ko'pdan ko'p aql chiqar.
4. Ko'p yoyilsa, yo'q topilar/ Ko'pdan quyon qutulmas.
5. . Ko'p ko'padi, Oz cho'kadi /Ko'pda karam bor.
6. Ko'plashgan yov qaytarar/ Ko'pni yomonlagan ko'milar.
7. Ko'pni yomonlagan ko'muvsiz qolar/ Ko'pni yomonlaganning o'zi yomon.
8. Ko'pni sevgan bimi sevmay/ Ko'pning ishi yitmas, Ozning ishi bitmas.
9. Ko'pning kuchi — karomat/ Ko'pning kuchi ko'lday, Ko'chib yurgan yelday. Ko'pning ko'lankasi — oltin/ Ko'pning rizqi — ko'l. Ko'pning qo'li ko'p.

Elliptical sentence in English proverbs:

All that glitters is not gold/A bird in the hand is worth two in the bush.

When in Rome, do as the Romans do/ Don't count your chickens before they hatch. Two wrongs don't make a right/ Absence makes heart grow fonder.

A fool and his money are soon parted/ After victory, tighten your helmet chord.

All is well that ends well/ All is fair in love and war.

Among the blind, one-eyed man is king. An empty vessel makes much noise.

Ellipsis is widely studied in the theoretical literature, central issues including the mental representation of elided material, the conditions which license ellipsis, and the means by which the elided material is recovered. One challenge to theoretical accounts of ellipsis comes from cases where the elided material does not appear to be a constituents. Since syntactic operations can only target constituents in standard phrase-structural approaches, accounts within these frameworks must posit additional movement operations to explain

such cases. These movement rules raise non-elided material out of a constituent, allowing ellipsis to apply only to the material that is left, thus creating the illusion of ellipsis applying to a non-constituent. Some alternative analyses assume more flexible conceptions of syntactic units such as the catena, thus allowing ellipsis to directly target non-constituents without the need for additional movement rules.

References:

- 1.Ágel, V., Ludwig Eichinger, Hans-Werner Eroms, Peter Hellwig, Hans Heringer, and Hennig Lobin (eds.) 2003/6. Dependency and Valency: An international handbook of contemporary research. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter.
- 2.Johnson, Kyle 2001. What VP ellipsis can do, and what it can't, but not why. In The handbook of contemporary syntactic theory, ed. Mark Baltin and Chris Collins, 439–479. Oxford: Blackwell Publishers.
- 3.Lappin, Shalom 1996. The interpretation of ellipsis. In The handbook of contemporary semantic theory, ed. Shalom Lappin. Oxford: Blackwell.
- 4.Lobeck, Anne. 1995. Ellipsis: Functional heads, licensing, and identification. New York: Oxford University Press.
- 5.Lobeck, Anne. 2006. Ellipsis in DP. In The Blackwell Companion to Syntax, ed. by Martin Everaert et al., vol. 2, pp. 145–173. Oxford: Blackwell.
- 6.Merchant, Jason. 2001. The syntax of silence: Sluicing, islands, and the theory of ellipsis. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- 7.Osborne, Timothy and Thomas Groß 2012. Constructions are catenae: Construction Grammar meets Dependency Grammar. *Cognitive Linguistics* 23, 1: 163–214.
- 8.G'ofurova Mavluda Botirjon kizi /lingucultural aspect of barbarisms in english and uzbek /JOURNAL OF AERONAUTICAL MATERIALS ISSN: 1005-5053 /Vol. 42, Issue-05, 2022 pp.257-262

